

ONLINE TRAVEL AND TOURISM STARTUPS IN INDIA: BUSINESS MODELS & GROWTH CHALLENGES

Dr. M.K Badri Narayanan

Associate Professor

MBA - School of Management

Hindustan University, Kelambakam, Chennai, India

S. P. Deepika

Research Scholar

MBA - School of Management

Hindustan University, Chennai, India

Abstract

Indian online travel market is growing at a steady rate due to increased awareness, ease of access and cost-effective solutions. India is expected to be home to the fastest growing online travel market in the Asia-Pacific region with gross bookings expected to touch \$24 billion and \$7.1 billion respectively. Online travel is the driving force in the e-commerce segment, with a global contribution of 70 per cent of all e-commerce activities and its importance is likely to increase in the future. The Online Travel Agency is in its infancy with opportunities for capable new ventures. Various offers and deals from the OTAs have made the market very lucrative for the customers, thus driving competition. The Indian OTA market is growing at a rapid rate of about 35 per cent, but the space is cluttered with multiple players. The main trigger has been the low investment required in the online domain. Also, there is an added convenience to a traveler for booking tickets, comparing the fare rates and choosing destinations. This paper presents a comparison of successful startups in the domain of OTA, traces the entrepreneurial persona, innovative business models, and growth/sustainability challenges of selected startups in India.

Keywords: *Online Travel Agency, entrepreneurial persona, Business models, Competition, Opportunities*

Introduction

The tourism industry has undergone a variety of changes throughout the last years. One of the main reasons can be found in the increased globalization which respectively leads to an easier access and dissemination of information as well as a borderless world offering completely new opportunities for travelers nowadays (Buhalis & Law, 2008). Another important development in this regard, is the emergence of the internet and so called ICTs, which account for all the information and communication technologies used in a company including hardware as well as software and tools such as websites or management information systems (Osterwalder, 2004). These ICTs enable customers to attain reliable and accurate information and also make it possible to undertake reservations in a faster and often more convenient way than offered by conventional methods such as high street travel agencies (Buhalis & O'Connor, 2005). Furthermore, e-tourism encourages a more interactive relationship between tourism organizations and travelers which lead to completely new ways of developing and marketing tourism products. As Buhalis and Licata (2002) state the Internet gave rise to numerous new tourism eMediators who distribute their products directly to consumers. In addition, to the technological changes also the customer behavior of travelers changed. Therefore, due to the change in customer behavior, the travel industry needs to adopt new business model innovations in order to satisfy the more demanding consumers nowadays.

Online Travel Agencies (OTA's) – the emerging domain

The potential of travel industry is very vast but along with opportunities, the competition is also intense in this sector. With the growing Internet penetration, the online travel space in the country is getting bigger and more and more people are depending on online facilities to book their travel. Travel is now about a unique, memorable and seamless experience and the evolving consumer does his share of research to get the best deals befitting his plan. So, it is important for travel entrepreneurs to stand apart from the crowd. The share of online travel bookings currently stands at 30 per cent and is expected to rise exponentially as the internet penetration increases in the country.

According to a recent IMRB and IAMAI report, the number of internet users has touched the 100 million mark and is expected to grow rapidly, especially with mobiles/ smart-phones also contributing to internet access. The growth drivers include such as rising disposable income coupled with proliferation of the internet, which has increased online traffic considerably. This study examines the Business models of selected startups in this domain and also their growth challenges.

Tourism Entrepreneurship Literature:

The following literature on tourism entrepreneurship is of relevance to the subject of this study

- Entrepreneurship plays an important role in economic growth, innovation and in poverty alleviation (Landes, 1998). Despite the fact the development of entrepreneurship in tourism could be a way to fully involved and benefit the local population and probably enable the tourism industry to account for a higher percentage of the GDP in those developing countries, it is the most understudied economic phenomenon today (Lingelbach, 2005)
- Bishal Bhattarai in his project titled “Impact of e-commerce in Travel and Tourism industry and challenges for adopting it” has studied on travel and tourism industry along with their impact on this industry after adaption of e-commerce. He has suggested that companies adapting e-commerce should focus on changing behavior of customer as well, what customer expects while booking and buying through the web.
- Regarding travel decisions, several studies report consistently high usage and importance of internet sources (Bieger and Laesser, 2004; Bonn et al., 1999; Susskind et al., 2003; Cai et al., 2004). The internet has also become an important sales channel for the travel industry, because it is associated with comparably lower distribution and sales costs, but also because it adapts to the high supply and demand dynamics in this industry (Harris and Duckworth, 2005; Schwartz and Zea, 1999). Consequently, the travel and tourism industry tries to increase the internet-specific share of sales volumes.
- Online travel agencies (OTA) first occurred in the 1990s after the emergence of the Internet. Pioneering companies in this field are firms such as Expedia Inc. and Orbitz, who established a strong market position in the online tourism sector. Similar to traditional high street travel agencies, they also act as an intermediary between travel - related products as well as information and customers (Kim et al., 2007). However, OTAs only operate online and do not engage in any offline channels to reach their target customers. They provide the online purchaser with the possibility to put together their own customized holiday by selecting a flight, hotel or potential car rental individually. The main advantage in addition to the great flexibility is the saving of costs in terms of travel agent fees (Buhalis, 1998).

Though there are various studies carried out based on online travel agencies, a gap is observed on the startup online ventures with the business model canvas comparison. There is a need for such a study to fill the gap in literature. In this background, this study has been pursued with the following objectives:

- To trace the potential of emerging domain of online Travel industry in India
- To analyze the Business models adopted by selected startup ventures
- To highlight the opportunities and challenges for Online Travel Agency (OTA) startups

Methodology

This is a descriptive study based on secondary data collected from the entrepreneur interviews and articles published in financial dailies. For this study, nine online tour operators which have been featured in popular financial dailies, identified as successful OTA startups, were purposively selected for the study. They are Cleartrip, Girls on the Go Club, Thrillophilia, White Collar Hippiie, Tripoto, Padhaaro, Bharat Travels, Detours India and Must See India. The theoretical model of Business Model Canvas has been used to analyze the different dimensions of the business model adopted by the selected OTAs. Also a SWOT analysis has been done to highlight the opportunities and challenges for these startups.

Limitations of the study

- Only the selected startup ventures are concentrated
- The study is limited only to India

India's Domestic Tourism Sector – in its growth trajectory

Table 1: Number of Domestic Tourist Visits (DTVs) to all States/UTs in India, 1997-2013

Year	No. of Domestic Tourist Visits to States/UTs (in Million)	Percentage (%) change over the previous year
1997	159.88	14.1
1998	168.2	5.2
1999	190.67	13.4
2000	220.11	15.4
2001	236.47	7.4
2002	269.6	14.0
2003	309.04	14.6
2004	366.27	18.5
2005	392.01	7.0
2006	462.32	17.9
2007	526.56	13.9
2008	563.03	6.9
2009	668.8	18.8
2010	747.7	11.8
2011	864.53	15.6
2012	1045.05	20.9
2013 (P)	1145.28	9.6

Source: State/ Union Territory Tourism Departments

Popular perceptions of tourists tend to be quite narrowly defined, as persons traveling to leisure resorts or tourist destinations or on religious pilgrimage. The Tourism and Hospitality industry is one of the largest segments under the services sector of the Indian economy. Tourism in India is a key growth driver and a significant source of foreign exchange earnings. In India, the sector's direct contribution to gross domestic product (GDP) is expected to grow at 7.8 percent per annum during the period 2013-2023. The following table shows the Number of Domestic Tourist Visits to all states/UTs in India from 1997 – 2013. The tourism sector in India is flourishing due to an increase in foreign tourist arrivals (FTA) and a larger number of Indians travelling to domestic destinations.

Chart 1: Domestic Tourist Visits to all states/UTs in India, 1997-2013

According to statistics available with the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), revenues gained from domestic tourism rose by 5.1 per cent in 2013 and is expected to increase by 8.2 per cent this year. India is projected to be number one for growth globally in the wellness tourism sector in the next five years, clocking over 20 per cent gains annually through 2017, according to a study conducted by SRI International. The government's decision to introduce the electronic visa facility (e-Visa) will give a much needed boost to inbound travel in India. Enforcing the electronic travel authorization (ETA) before the next tourism season, which starts in November, will result in a clear jump of at least 15 per cent, and this is only the start, as per Mr. Madhavan Menon, Managing Director, Thomas Cook India.

Thus there is a clear emerging opportunity for new entities to enter into this sector. As the industry is emerging, the market is also fragmented and is oligopolistic in nature. The industry is also characterized by high bargaining power of both suppliers and customers. Moreover, there is no entry barrier which poses competitive threats by new entrants. Hence it is essential to understand for the existing businesses to understand the business well and strengthen themselves in key areas by building their competitiveness.

OTAs – A Niche

New ventures are classified into five major categories – Revolutionary, Niche, propagators, hustle and speculative. Niche ventures need not be a radical concept or idea; they attempt to serve segments with a unique need, not served by mainstream offerings. They offer simple and easy to use product or service and require modest

managerial and leadership skills. It suits entrepreneurs with moderate growth/wealth ambitions and limited resources. The Online Tour Agencies (OTA) Startups are clearly under the category of niche ventures.

Strategy towards Service Quality

The strategies used by these startup domains are simple, comprehensive, reliable and responsible. They believe in travelling with limited people so that they can provide their fullest service by giving individual attention. Online agency providing services exclusively for women, always concentrates on their safety. For that, bouncers are accompanied with the travelers. The agencies always believe on connecting the right customer with the right service provider by maintaining a strong relationship with their partners and agents. All these agencies provide customized and personalized services based on which pricing is done.

The Business Model Canvas

Table 2: The Business model canvas

Pillars	Building Block of Business model	Description
Product	Value Proportions	Gives an overall view of a company's bundle of Products and Services
Customer Interface	Customer Segments	Describes the segments of customers a company wants to offer value to.
	Channels	Describes the various means of the company to get in touch with its customers.
	Customer relationships	Explains the kind of link a company establishes between itself and its different customer segments.
Infrastructure Management	Key Resources	Describes the assets required to offer and deliver the previous elements...
	Key Activities	...by performing a number of activities arranged in a specific way.
	Key Partnerships	Portrays the network of cooperative agreements with other companies necessary to efficiently offer and commercialize value
Financial Aspects	Revenue Streams	Describes the way a company makes money through a variety of revenue flows.
	Cost Structure	Sums up the monetary consequences of the means employed in the business model.

Source: The nine building blocks of a business model (synthesis of Osterwalder, 2004 and Osterwalder and Pigneur,2009)

The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management and lean startup template for developing new or documenting existing business models. It is a visual chart with elements describing a firm's value proposition, infrastructure, customers, and finances. It assists firms in aligning their activities by illustrating potential trade-offs. Formal descriptions of the business become the building blocks for its activities. The following are the business model canvas for selected startups in online travel agency domain in India.

Value Proportions

The value proposition defines how items of value (product and service features as well as complementary services) are packaged and offered to fulfill customer needs. It gives an overall view of one of the firm's bundles of products and services that together represent value for a specific customer segment. It describes the way a firm differentiates itself from its competitors and is the reason why customers buy from a certain firm and not from another. The value propositions may be Quantitative – price and efficiency or Qualitative – overall customer experience and outcome. The Products and Services offered by these selected startups are mostly for niche segment which includes customized and personalized tour packages, adventure tourism, and guided tour accompanied by local experts. The value proposition is pre-dominantly aimed at providing cost-effective and customized services to their niche customers which differentiate the OTA's from their competitors.

Customer Segments

The customer segment can be defined as the different groups of people or organizations an enterprise aims to reach. Customers comprise the heart of any business model. In order to better satisfy customers, a company may group them into distinct segments with common needs, common behaviors or other attributes. The various customer segments targeted by these selected startup OTA's are Frequent Travelers, Businessmen/women, single lady traveler, activity travel segment, groups and weekend getaway. The basic strategy adopted by these OTA's are based on cost, differentiation, focused group and combination of cost and focus.

Channels

When the customer segments are identified the value propositions need to be connected to their subsequent markets.

This can be done by selecting one or more suitable distribution channels, allowing the company to deliver value to its target customers. A distribution channel describes how a company communicates with and reaches its customer segments to deliver a value proposition. The channels used by these OTA's are partners in other regions/countries where they do not operate but provide services, ground handling people at the destination who take care of the guest who comes through these OTA's. These people also acts as local guide and service providers. Thus the channel partners also become the key partners to the OTAs and their linkages become a key resource which the OTAs draw upon.

Customer Relationship

Relationships can range from personal to automate and may be driven by different motivations. The motivation for maintaining a relationship with a customer can either be customer acquisition, customer retention or boosting sales. The customer relationships called for by a company's business model deeply influence the overall customer experience. While Girls on the Go Club and Thrillophilia offer dedicated customer service, Clear Trip and Must See offer co-creation to build customer relationships. Also the OTAs concentrate on customer relationship by actively engaging them through membership, social networks by keeping them up to date, subscription and newsletter.

Key Resources

Every business model requires assets or key resources to let the model function. These resources allow a company to create and offer a value proposition, reach markets, maintain relationships with customer segments and earn revenues. Key resources are physical, financial, intellectual or human. Key resources can be owned or leased by the company or acquired from key partners. In the case of OTAs, to keep their cost-advantage, they resort to outsourcing and partnering. Hence those channel partners, their strong local presence, becomes a key resource on which the OTAs draw upon. This leads to a high bargaining power of these partners. This is a challenge for these startup-OTAs.

Key Activities

Each company needs to perform a number of activities to successfully fulfill the customer's needs. The key activities are those activities that are of the utmost importance to the company and let it operate successfully. Key activities differ depending on the business model type. The Key activities of these OTA's are customized and personalized. Based on the type of the customer segment, their activities differ.

Key Partners

The Key Partners for these OTA's are the agent who does the ground operations for these people. In order to optimize operations and reduce risks of a business model, these organizations cultivate buyer-supplier relationships so they can focus on their core activity. Most of the selected startup OTA's work on the basis of partnership in various countries they operate. This involves lot of risk and uncertainty as the service providers might get the actual OTA's business by providing services at lesser cost when compared to them.

Revenue Streams

The income a company generates from each customer segment is represented in the revenue streams element of the business model. The revenue streams for these OTA's are the income from sold travel products and revenue from commission or flat fee of each transaction. While pre-dominantly the startup-OTAs adopt fixed pricing mechanisms viz., List Price, Product feature dependent pricing and Customer segment dependent pricing, due to their limited bargaining power, they also adopt dynamic pricing with corporate and bulk orders.

Cost Structure

The cost structure element describes all costs incurred to operate a business model. Creating and delivering value, maintaining customer relationships and generating revenue all incur costs. The OTAs have a necessity to adopt a Cost Driven approach which includes maintenance of lean cost structure, low price value proposition, maximum automation and extensive outsourcing. The cost structure of these OTA's involves agent's fee, commission, employees, sales and marketing and general overheads. But being niche players, their positioning with the customers are at times Value Driven, where they shall have a struggle to provide premium value proposition at a lesser cost. With limited bargaining power with the suppliers and customers, this dichotomous status, shall be a major challenge.

Emerging Challenges for this Startup domain

Micro Level

- Most of the agencies target the niche segment which would be a challenge in giving them a convincing package
- Scaling up shall be a problem, since the demand is to serve every customer who asks for a customized and personalized package.
- Since their positioning with the customers are at times Value Driven, where they shall have a struggle to provide premium value proposition at a lesser cost. With limited bargaining power with the suppliers and customers, this dichotomous status, shall be a major challenge.
- With a high dependence on key partners, there is a danger of their customers being poached by the partners, who in turn shall become their competitors.
- Replicating the promised services by the company by the agents is difficult. The agents should not spoil the essence of the promised service

Macro Level

- There is no clear policy support for these online ventures
- The market is very fragmented with limited entry barriers, which shall affect the consolidation of this industry, which is aggravated by the vacuum in policy.
- With scaling up being an issue, the emerging growth opportunity shall lead to further fragmentation.

SWOT Analysis

The SWOT analysis is performed for every individual business model element following the model proposed by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2009),The following are the SWOT analysis for the selected startup online domains

Table 3: SWOT Analysis

STRENGTH	WEAKNESS
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ The value proposition is well aligned with customer needs.▪ The current channel (travel agents) is an effective way of reaching a significant part of the market▪ Execution quality of key activities is high▪ Good Customer support▪ Tieups with airlines, corporates and hotel chains	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Customer churn rates are high▪ The key resources can easily be replicated by competitors▪ Customer Relationship Management▪ Operating on the same model

OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Serving new customer segments▪ Increasing customer follow up, tightening existing relationships▪ Untapped International tourist market▪ Effective utilization of employees	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ New Entrants▪ High dependence on Partners and agents▪ Technological advantage which is easily available for competitors to build as well, hence not a sustainable advantage.

The SWOT analysis shows that there few critical components in the current business model. They are, involving lot of agents, customized and personalized services. This involves a lot of risk, as there are chances for the agents to take over the business by providing the services at lesser rate than the OTAs. The OTAs cannot always provide customized and personalized packages as it involves increase in costs and also providing the same experience every time will be difficult. The companies can also tap the other segments rather than concentrating on the same group. Customer relationship should also be concentrated in order to survive in the market for a longer period so far the strong value proposition has kept the company in business.

Conclusion

In this study, the business model of the selected online startup travel agencies was reviewed. The analysis shows that the business model meets the basic demands of its customers but it misses out on a number of opportunities which could make the model stronger and the company more profitable. The business model element together with their challenges is also discussed. The current value proposition is strong and incorporates many value elements that are regarded to be essential according to the best practices (e.g. flexibility, service, tailor-made and value for money). However there are a number of value elements that should be added to the value proposition to increase its strength. First of all creating a strong brand with well known brand values will enhance the awareness and trustworthiness of the company. Secondly creating customer relationships which enable personalizing and focusing the company's offering. Finally acquiring detailed knowledge will enhance the travel experience of the customers. Since there are no customer relationships at the moment this provides a great opportunity for improving customer retention, customer acquisition and up selling. Improving customer follow-up and tightening the relationship with the customer is possible by directly selling to the customer. In order to survive in the market, these OTAs can concentrate on the other untapped segments which would increase their business or else it would be difficult for them to convince the existing customers to utilize the same sort of services.

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